

Search for variable stars in the open cluster Gulliver 35

R.G. Karimov,¹ A.S. Hojaev.¹

¹ Ulugh Beg Astronomical Institute, Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, 33 Astronomicheskaya str., Tashkent, 100052, Uzbekistan

Abstract

We present preliminary results of the analysis of TESS light curves and GAIA DR3 data in the region of the open cluster Gulliver 35 in order to search for variable stars and more comprehensive study of the hosted open cluster. 30 variable stars of various types have been identified in the cluster region. The analysis of new variables was carried out together with the main parameters of the cluster.

1 Introduction

Undoubtedly, variable stars are a useful tool for improving our understanding of the structure and evolution of stars. In turn, stars are born in groups and form star clusters, which are a group of stars with the same age, distance, initial composition and a wide range of masses, and allow us to determine the physical characteristics of stars and their evolutionary status. The observational search and study of various types of variable stars in star clusters using ground-based telescopes has been carried out by different authors for a long time (Ambartsumian & Mirzoyan (1975), Delgado *et al.* (1984), Kaluzny *et al.* (1993), Herbst *et al.* (1994)). But the opportunities provided by the Kepler and TESS space missions to search for exoplanet transits, the by-product of which were time series for a large number of stars, have significantly increased interest in such studies. The data from the Kepler and TESS missions, along with a review of the GAIA mission, which provided massive amounts of data on the intrinsic properties of the billions of stars, make it possible to study not only star clusters, but also their populations including variable stars and the processes occurring in them in more detail.

2 Object and methods

The aim of this study is to search for variable stars in an open star cluster using TESS mission data, analyze light curves, and determine whether variable stars belong to a star cluster. The object of study is the open star cluster Gulliver 35 and the variable stars located in the region of this cluster. The radius of the cluster containing half of its members is $5.4'$ Cantat-Gaudin & Anders (2020). Gulliver 35 (RA = $10^h01^m31.0^s$, DEC = $-58^\circ11'53''$, J2000) is a quite distant (2127 ± 108 pc) with parallax (0.411 ± 0.27) mas, proper motion ($\mu_\alpha \cos \delta$, $\mu_\delta = -6.961 \pm 0.081$, 3.982 ± 0.083) mas yr⁻¹, age ($\log(\text{age}) = 7.839 \pm 0.394$) yr, and metallicity (Fe/H = 0.267) Dias *et al.* (2021) open star cluster located in the southern hemisphere.

In the current work, the GAIA DR3 data are used to determine whether the variable stars found in the region belong to the cluster. For the analysis of astrometric data, the pyUPMASK package Pera *et al.* (2021) is used, which is an unsupervised clustering method for stellar clusters based on the gen-

eral UPMASK algorithm Krone-Martins & Moitinho (2014). To search for variable stars in the cluster region, TESS mission data and the PYTHON package *Lightkurve* Lightkurve Collaboration *et al.* (2018) are used to analyze the time series and study the variable stars. This package is a useful tool to access archive Kepler and TESS data from Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST) server, it allows to analyze light curves, remove outliers, detrend, normalize light curves, build various types of periodograms, remove systematics etc.

Figure 1: Example of light curves for some variable stars located in the region of the open cluster Gulliver 35.

3 Results and discussion

Based on the results of time series analysis, 30 variable stars of various types were identified. Although this region of the star cluster has been studied in projects to search for transients and other variable objects, only 1 of these 30 variable stars turned out to be a known rotational variable, and

the remaining 29 stars are candidates for new variable stars. Some of the variable stars detected in course of this project are indeed binary stars, several of which are Algol-type ones. As an example, a few representative light curves of discovered variable stars are presented in Figure 1. Half of the

Figure 2: Histogram of the distribution of parallaxes of all probable members of the open cluster Gulliver 35 according to our sample and literature data (marked with open bins) and variable stars (marked with filled bins).

Figure 3: VPD of the open cluster Gulliver 35.

variable stars are within the probable radius of the Gulliver 35 cluster, but according to the Gaia data, only 7 stars were found to be within a star cluster distance (Figure 2), and the remaining variables are foreground stars.

In the Figure 3 we present the vector point diagram of the open cluster Gulliver 35, where crosses mark variable stars and points mark all probable members of the cluster. The diagram of spatial distribution of stars in open cluster, where the solid circles mark all probable members of the cluster according to our selection and literature sources, open circles mark variable stars located in the cluster region, presented in figure 4.

The position of these stars on the color-magnitude (see Figure 5) and vector point diagrams suggests that a number of these stars may be associated with the cluster. However, according to our preliminary analysis of a sample of variable stars using GAIA data and comparison with the pub-

lished probability of stars belonging to this cluster according to Cantat-Gaudin *et al.* (2018), only one variable star of the cluster was chosen as probable member. Our analysis and interpretation of data from the open cluster Gulliver 35 continues.

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of stars in the open cluster Gulliver 35.

Figure 5: Color-magnitude diagram of the open cluster Gulliver 35. Filled circles mark all probable members of the cluster according to our selection and literature data, the open circles mark variable stars located in the cluster region, gray dots mark field stars.

Acknowledgments

This work has made use of data from the European Space Agency (ESA) mission GAIA, the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite mission (TESS).

The authors thanks Ministry of Innovation Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for funding the joint project UZB-Ind-2021-99, in frame of which the work is being implemented.

References

Ambartsumian, V. A. & Mirzoyan, L. V. 1975, In *Variable Stars and Stellar Evolution*, edited by Sherwood & Plaut,

- Proceedings of the Symposium, Moscow, USSR, July 29-August 4, 1974. Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing Co., pp. 3–14.
- Cantat-Gaudin, T. & Anders, F. 2020, *A&A*, 121, 99.
- Cantat-Gaudin, T., Jordi, C., Vallenari, A., Bragaglia, A., Balaguer-Nunez, L., *et al.* 2018, *A&A*, 618, 16.
- Delgado, A. J., Alfaro, E. J., Garcia-Pelayo, J. M., Garrido, R., & Vidal, S. 1984, *A&A*, 58, 447.
- Dias, W. S., Monteiro, H., Moitinho, A., Lepine, J. R. D., Carraro, G., *et al.* 2021, *MNRAS*, 504, 356.
- Herbst, W., Herbst, D. K., Grossman, E. J., & Weinstein, D. 1994, *AJ*, 108, 1906.
- Kaluzny, J., Mazur, B., & Krzeminski, W. 1993, *MNRAS*, 262, 49.
- Krone-Martins, A. & Moitinho, A. 2014, *A&A*, 561, 12.
- Lightkurve Collaboration, Cardoso, J. V. d. M., Hedges, C., Gully-Santiago, M., Saunders, N., *et al.* 2018, *Lightkurve: Kepler and TESS time series analysis in Python*. Astrophysics Source Code Library.
- Pera, M. S., Perren, G. I., Moitinho, A., Navone, H. D., & Vazquez, R. A. 2021, *A&A*, 650, 13.